

Immediate Actions: Road-Network Accesses Preservation

PORTO ALEGRE AND ITS METROPOLITAN REGION VULNERABILITY ANALYSIS – MAY 2024 FLOODINGS

Total Road Elements
405.631

Flooded
56.549 (13.9%)

Operational
349.082 (86.1%)

BR-290 & BR-116

Humanitarian Corridor:
Emergency and relief route

Flooded Areas - 08/05/2024

Preferential Routes Hierarchies:

High Low

Important Road Interruptions:

- BR-290** – Roads between Porto Alegre and Eldorado do Sul municipalities (Guaíba's Bridge)
- BR-448** – Several interruptions between Canoas e São Leopoldo municipalities
- BR-116** – Interruptions between Canoas e São Leopoldo municipalities
- BR-386 e RS-240** – Partial interruptions towards Montenegro municipality (Cai River Bridge Accesses)

Considering the Canoas airport as a logistical hub (marked on map):

- Routes to Porto Alegre:** RS-118, BR-116 & BR-290, Av. das Industrias – Cachoeirinha
- Routes to Canoas:** BR-116, Santos Ferreira Avenue
- Routes to Cachoeirinha/Gravatá:** Santos Ferreira Avenue, Boqueirão Avenue, Av. das Industrias
- Routes to the Vale dos Sinos:** RS-020 (Taquara and Parobé), RS-239 (towards Sao Leopoldo)
- Routes to Triunfo e Montenegro:** partially interrupted
- Routes to Guaíba e Eldorado do Sul:** interrupted
- Routes from Rio Grande do Sul's coastline (unaffected area):** RS-040 (Porto Alegre, Alvorada Viamão; RS-030 (Gravatá, Cachoeirinha and Canoas)

Critical road accesses to the metropolitan region cohesion:

- **RS-118 (Only fully operational redundancy in the system)**
- **BR-290 (Humanitarian corridor - Castello Branco Avenue)**
- **BR-116 (Canoas airbase access – only functional airport)**
- **RS-020 & RS-239 (Vale dos Sinos regional access)**

Access through RS-118 is the only fully operational one and constitutes the only redundancy of the road network that connects Greater Porto Alegre. **It must be protected at all costs.**

The humanitarian corridor (BR-290) allows for a redundancy between Porto Alegre's city centre and Canoas' airbase (BR-116).

BR-290 e BR-116: Attention needed: partially operational, due to road damage and flooded road elements.

Phases of post-disaster recovery:

The road-network analysis aids in planning all three phases of post-disaster recovery.

Efforts are centered on elaborating fit-for-purpose information for planning and executing the **preparation** and **response** phases.